

INTERACTION OF THIONYL CHLORIDE AND NAPHTHOLS IN PRESENCE OF FINELY DIVIDED COPPER

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Interaction of thionyl chloride and α -naphthol in presence of finely divided copper in ethereal solution furnishes 4:4'-dichlorodinaphthyl-1-sulphide (I) and 4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide (III), whereas β -naphthol under similar conditions affords 2:2'-dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide (II). The dibromo, diacetoxy, dibenzoyloxy and dimethoxy derivatives of (II) as well as their nitration products are described.

When thionyl chloride was allowed to react with α -naphthol in presence of finely divided copper in ethereal solution, two products were formed, both being insoluble in ether. The solid, left after removal of ether and excess of thionyl chloride, was first extracted with alcohol. The paste left after removal of alcohol was extracted with benzene, when one product (I) remained insoluble, which was found to contain chlorine and sulphur, and it was not soluble in alkali.

The brown paste, obtained after removal of benzene, was treated with sodium carbonate when a yellow solid (II) was obtained containing sulphur only. It was soluble in alkali and it afforded diacetoxy, dibenzoyloxy and dimethoxy derivatives.

With bromine, (II) afforded a compound containing both bromine and sulphur. The dibromo sulphide on treatment with fuming nitric acid furnished a compound which was found identical with 2-bromo-4-nitro-1-naphthol, prepared according to Hodgson and Elliot (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1852), by mixed m.p.

When fuming nitric acid was allowed to react at 100° with (II), it afforded 4-nitro-1-naphthol, identical with the one prepared according to Deninger (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1889, 40, 300). The sulphide (II) was therefore assigned the constitution 4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide. As (I) did not contain the hydroxy group but chlorine, it was assigned the constitution 4:4'-dichlorodinaphthyl-1-sulphide. The same sulphide (II) was also formed when α -naphthol was allowed to react with sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride in ethereal solution only for 1 hour. Airan and Shah (*this Journal*, 1945, 22, 359) carried out this reaction, but could not isolate any product in the case of sulphur dichloride reaction and the product they obtained with the monochloride had m. p. 212° to which they assigned the formula $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$. Onufrowicz (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3368) has reported the formation of trisulphide by the action of sulphur monochloride in benzene solution at 0°. No such higher sulphides could be isolated in the present work.

When β -naphthol in ethereal solution was allowed to react with thionyl chloride in presence of copper, a compound ($C_{20}H_{14}O_2S$) melting at 220° was obtained. It was found identical with the mono-sulphide described by Airan and Shah (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1940, 9, Part III, 120; 1942, 10, Part IV, 129; *this Journal*, 1945, 22, 363) and also by Henrique (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2998) although these authors recorded its m.p. as 212°. It showed no depression in m.p. with the substance prepared according to the method of Henrique (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

4 : 4'-Dichlorodinaphthyl-1-sulphide (I).—Thionyl chloride (5 c. c.) was added to the mixture of α -naphthol (5 g.), copper powder (4 g.) and dry ether (30 c. c.), kept in a cold-water bath. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 1 hour, with occasional shaking. Ether and the excess of thionyl chloride were filtered off and the residue was well washed with dry ether. The residue was then extracted with alcohol. The paste, obtained after removal of alcohol, was boiled with benzene when a greenish solid (I) remained behind and a brownish paste was obtained after removal of benzene. (I) was found insoluble in alkali. It crystallised from alcohol but the crystals did not melt up to 300° , yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 3.5; Cl, 19.8; S, 9.05. $C_{20}H_{12}Cl_2S$ requires C, 67.6; H, 3.38; Cl, 20.0; S, 9.01 per cent).

It is insoluble in acetic acid, carbon disulphide, chloroform, benzene and ether, sparingly soluble in acetone and fairly soluble in alcohol.

4 : 4'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide (II).—The brownish paste in the above experiment was triturated with sodium carbonate solution when a yellow solid was obtained. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. $118-19^\circ$, yield 2 g. It is soluble in alkali and in most of the common solvents except acetic acid and ether. (Found: C, 75.1; H, 4.2; S, 10.3. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 75.48; H, 4.4; S, 10.07 per cent).

The same sulphide (II) was formed when α -naphthol (5 g.) was allowed to react with sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride (5 c. c.) in presence of dry ether (30 c. c.). The paste, obtained after removal of ether and the excess of sulphur chloride, was worked up as in the above experiment; yield 2 g. in each case.

Diacetyl derivative of (II) was prepared by boiling it for 1 hour with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. $235-36^\circ$. (Found: S, 8.04. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4S$ requires S, 7.9 per cent).

3 : 3'-Dinitro-4 : 4'-diacetyloxidinaphthyl-1-sulphide was formed when the diacetyl derivative of (II, 1 g.), suspended in acetic acid (20 c. c.), was heated at 100° for half an hour with HNO_3 (conc., 20 c. c.) and then left overnight at room temperature. The solid obtained on dilution was boiled with acetic acid and the residue was crystallised from a mixture of nitrobenzene and acetic acid, m.p. $250-51^\circ$. (Found: N, 5.5; S, 6.2. $C_{24}H_{16}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 5.7; S, 6.5 per cent).

Dimethyl ether of (II) was formed by heating on a boiling water-bath a mixture of (II, 1 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (10 c. c.) in presence of 10% NaOH solution (40 c. c.) for 4 hours. The product was crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. $140-41^\circ$. It was found insoluble in alkali. (Found: S, 9.36. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2S$ requires S, 9.25 per cent). It showed no lowering in m.p. when mixed with the substance prepared according to Loth and Michaelis (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2544).

3 : 3'-Dinitro-4 : 4'-dimethoxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide was prepared in the same way as the dinitro derivative of the diacetyl derivative of (II). It crystallised from a mixture of nitrobenzene and acetic acid, m.p. $102-103^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: S, 7.22. $C_{22}H_{16}O_6N_2S$ requires S, 7.34 per cent).

Dibenzoyl derivative of (II) was obtained by benzoylating it in presence of pyridine, and heating the reaction mixture on a boiling water-bath for about 4 hours. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 194-95°. (Found: S, 6.2. $C_{34}H_{22}O_4S$ requires S, 6.08 per cent).

3:3'-Dinitro-4:4'-dibenzoyldinaphthyl-1-sulphide was prepared in the same way as the other dinitro derivatives, described above. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 252-53°. (Found: S, 4.84. $C_{34}H_{20}O_4N_2S$ requires S, 5.19 per cent).

3:3'-Dibromo-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide.—The sulphide (II, 1 g.) was added to liquid bromine (5 c.c.) and the mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted with water and the solid separating was triturated with sodium bisulphite solution and finally crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: Br, 33.8. $C_{20}H_{12}O_2Br_2S$ requires Br, 33.58 per cent).

4-Nitro-1-naphthol.—The sulphide (II, 1 g.) was suspended in H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 c.c.), fuming nitric acid (10 c.c.) was added to it and the mixture was heated for 2 hours on a boiling water-bath and then poured over crushed ice, when a yellow product separated. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 164-65°. (Found: N, 7.2. Calc. for $C_{10}H_7O_2N$: N, 7.4 per cent).

4-Nitro-2-bromo-1-naphthol was obtained from 3:3'-dibromo-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide in the same way as 4-nitro-1-naphthol was obtained from sulphide (II). It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 235-36°. (Found: N, 5.1; Br, 29.8. Calc. for $C_{10}H_6O_2NBr$: N, 5.22; Br, 29.85 per cent). It showed no lowering in m.p. when mixed with a genuine specimen prepared according to Hodgson and Elliot (*loc. cit.*).

2:2'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl-1-sulphide (III).—Copper (4 g.) was added to the solution of β -naphthol (5 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (5 c.c.) was then gradually added to it. After about half an hour, ether and thionyl chloride were removed (at room temp.) and the residue was extracted with alcohol. The alcoholic solution furnished a solid on dilution with water. This crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 220-21°, yield 3 g. (Found: S, 10.2. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S$: S, 10.07 per cent).

It showed no depression in m.p. with the compound prepared according to Henricque (*loc. cit.*) by the interaction of β -naphthol and sulphur monochloride in chloroform solution.

The same sulphide (III) was also obtained by the interaction of sulphur dichloride (4 c.c.) and β -naphthol (5 g.) in presence of dry ether (30 c.c.) below 15°, when a white solid separated in about 10 minutes. It was filtered, washed and finally crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 220-21°, yield 3 g.